

SPASE 3.0 Accepted Use Cases

Prioritization

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Priority:

- **High**: $\geq 80\%$ or fundamental functionality.
Use cases 1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 18, 19, 23, 24, 25, 26, 30, 31, 32, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 49, 50, 51, 53, 54, 55, 59, 60, 61, 65, 66.
- **Medium**: $\geq 66.67\%$ or useful/desired functionality.
Use cases 4, 17, 20, 21, 22, 29, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 52, 56, 57, 58, 62.
- **Low**: supplementary functionality.
Use cases 3, 27, 28, 33, 46, 47, 48, 63, 64.

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Use Case 1

1. **Nov 2024 voting: 73.33%**

Priority: High

Notes: Minimum here is to indicate a connection between the mission and the dataset, potentially through the instrument record.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Teacher and curriculum developers, Data Scientists, Heliophysics software services]

Title: Discover data associated with a mission, observatory or named group of instruments.

Description: User wants to discover datasets associated with a mission, observatory, or instruments suite. The user navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface (website or API), types the name (full or short) of the mission or observatory into the search bar, and begins exploring the datasets linked to that term. The user prefers to work with newer/older data and uses the time span feature in the search result page to narrow down the numerous results.

Use Case 2

2. **Nov 2024 voting: 73.33%**

Priority: High

Notes: Need to allow use of a controlled vocabulary for measurement type and phenomenon with all of the associated subfields, potentially allowing for those to be external to SPASE.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists, Teacher and curriculum developers, Heliophysics software services]

Title: Discover data associated with a given measurement type or phenomenon

Description: User wants to discover datasets related to a given measurement type or phenomenon. The user navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface (website or API), types the measurement type or phenomenon term into the search bar, and begins exploring the datasets. The user prefers to work with newer/older data and uses the time span feature in the search result page to narrow down the numerous results.

Use Case 3

3. **Nov 2024 voting: 73.33%**

Priority: **Low**

Notes: (exclude documentation → use case 8), reference publication goes here, citations from dataset to publications not common?, provenance (dataset generated by software, collected by instrument) → use case (8, 12, **18**, 19)?, potentially belongs in the DataCite DOI metadata (not SPASE), which can then be imported through DataCite's API and Asclepius Broker/similar to give this information on the landing page.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Teacher and curriculum developers, Heliophysics software services, Journal/Publisher services, Agency representatives, Web search indexers]

Title: Find publications related to a given dataset.

Description: User uses the Heliophysics-wide search interface (website or API) to find publications related to a given dataset, accesses those publications via the related links, determined the most common time ranges from the dataset used by those publications, and when the majority of those publications were published.

Use Case 4

4. **Nov 2024 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: **Medium**

Notes:

Root question: Do we want to expand the scope of SPASE to represent data created in support of publications (researcher-contributed data) to be represented in SPASE? Do we leave this in DataCite? Choosing to leave in DataCite and not include in SPASE **does not** prevent their representation on Heliodata. Choosing to exclude these from SPASE also decreases the curation effort needed to support the high request rate expected from researcher-contributed data. A stated concern was imposing limits on what fields could be required in SPASE 3.0 if this use case were supported.

Answer: The intended functionality is to include these data in the Heliophysics-wide search interface. Incorporating this use case into SPASE 3.0 severely limits the required fields to be at most those required by DataCite, which is incompatible with other international infrastructures (e.g., the description field required by DCAT3). Since the intended functionality is well within reach without SPASE 3.0, the decision is to exclude this use case. We choose to include this as a use case to support in SPASE 3.0, *with the caveat that this should not prevent SPASE 3.0 from requiring fields that DataCite does not or the reverse* (e.g., the description field or the publisher).

Users: [Research data metadata contributors, Large research data metadata contributors, Curation Staff]

Title: Creating a SPASE record via Zenodo or other generalist repository.

Description: User is submitting a Heliophysics-related dataset to a generalist repository (e.g. Zenodo, Dryad). The person sees and selects an option to also create a SPASE

record for the dataset (to be also searchable in a Heliophysics-wide search interface). A small number of additional fields are added to the required entries in the interface, which the user is able to quickly complete. Recommended fields are highlighted in the interface with included explanation and motivation. The user chooses some or no additional metadata to contribute. The user obtains a DOI for the dataset within 5-10 minutes, the dataset is made immediately available through a Heliophysics-specific search interface, and a link to that search interface is given to the user via the submission interface.

Use Case 5

5. **Nov 2024 voting: 80%**

Priority: High

Notes: FORCE11 guidelines direct users to cite datasets with version-specific DOIs and also cite any reference publications (with their DOIs) associated with the dataset. Need to include a way to indicate reference publications for datasets in SPASE 3.0 (e.g. "CiteWith").

Users: [Research data metadata contributors, Large research data metadata contributors, Curation Staff, Automated curation services, Heliophysics software services]

Title: Retrieving a citation with a DOI (or PID) for a dataset with a SPASE record.

Description: Person previously created a DOI for a dataset using a generalist repository (e.g. Zenodo or Dryad) and selected the option to also create a SPASE record to be included in a Heliophysics-search interface. The user now requires a citation to the dataset. The user navigates to the Heliophysics-specific search interface, searches for and finds the dataset, and navigates to the landing page of the dataset. The user notices a button called 'cite this dataset' (or something similar) and clicks the button. The user is presented with a drop-down menu of all of the (or a sample of the most highly selected) possible formats in which to receive the dataset citation information. The user chooses an option and receives the citation information in the format or method desired.

Use Case 6

6. **Nov 2024 voting: 80%**

Priority: High

Notes: Need to allow use of a controlled vocabulary for region/subregion with all of the associated subfields, potentially allowing for those to be external to SPASE. See use case 1 about indicating the connection between the mission and the dataset.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists, General public, Students, Teacher and curriculum developers]

Title: Find a dataset from a specific mission, observatory or other named group of instruments for a specific region or subregion.

Description: User wants to find a dataset from a specific Mission that observed a specific region (e.g. SOHO observations of the Solar corona) but the user cannot remember the Author's name of the presentation from a conference, news article, or other resource. The user searches for the dataset using a phrase (e.g. mission name and some region contextual phrasing). The query returns a long list of results. User selects the known Mission from the buttons on the interface of the search results page. The user additionally selects the Observed Region from which the data should come. The query returns an acceptable number of results and the user browses the landing pages of a few of the results.

Use Case 7

7. **Nov 2024 voting: 80%**

Priority: High

Notes: The PI's name may not be unique, so need to support ORCID for the PI to disambiguate the name. The mission name is expected to be unique. NASA policy requires support for an identifier for mission in metadata (see SPD-41a section IV. D.).

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists, Teacher and curriculum developers, Students]

Title: Discovering a new dataset using the name of the mission, observatory or other named group of instruments and the PI's name.

Description: User hears from a colleague about a dataset they believe may be helpful to their current goal. The colleague only tells the user the mission name, and the PI's name. User types in the time span they are interested in, the mission name and the PI's name a long list of results are returned. User additionally selects the time span and the mission name in the interface options of the result page and the results are narrowed down acceptably.

Use Case 8

8. **Nov 2024 voting: 80%**

Priority: High

Notes: Links to other resources used to create the dataset fall into provenance and must be supported (e.g. version-specific DOI/reference to software used to create the dataset, previous versions of the dataset, etc). Metadata regarding items that cite the dataset can live elsewhere (e.g. citation tracking services). Links to documentation and reference publications should be supported.

User: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists, Teacher and curriculum developers]

Title: Finding resources related to a dataset.

Description: User seeks additional resources pertinent to a dataset. User navigates to

the landing page of the dataset using either an internet search engine, the dataset's PID, or the Heliophysics-wide search interface (website or API). User notices suggested related items to that dataset (such as publications, dataset documentation, software used to generate the dataset, software used to analyze the data, and so on). The user selects a couple of the related items to review. In an API call, the user would send the PID or exact dataset name via the API with a request for types of related items available, then further select the types of related items the API should return information on.

Use Case 9

9. **Nov 2024 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: High

Notes: Does not provide requirements for specific fields, but regarded as a critical service.

Users: [Agency representatives, Journal/Publisher services, Web search indexers, Heliophysics software services]

Title: Provide metadata to external services via API calls

Description: User requests metadata from the SPASE metadata registry to incorporate into their own search interfaces. The user has a predefined set of minimum metadata requirements for a given dataset to be included in their search interface. The user requests this set of minimum metadata for all datasets in the SPASE metadata registry. The metadata required is returned by the metadata registry, via an API call. Any metadata requested by the user but not available is not returned but an error code is instead returned.

Use Case 10

10. **Nov 2024 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: High

Notes: Does not provide requirements for specific fields, but regarded as a critical characteristic.

Users: [Mission data metadata contributors, Research data metadata contributors, Large research data metadata contributors]

Title: Somebody who is not a SPASE expert can create a "minimally compliant" SPASE record in less than 5-10 minutes.

Description: User wants to create a SPASE record for their item. User navigates to the SPASE record submission form. The record submission form contains a list of several metadata fields available to be filled out by the User. The User does not have the information to fill out every metadata field, nor are they required to. Above each metadata field on the submission form the requirement level for the field is clearly

indicated. The labels are so easily seen by the User that the User can see all the Required fields upon first glance at the submission form. The User is not overwhelmed by the amount of available metadata fields and chooses to fill out the bare minimum Required fields. The User submits the record to be reviewed by Curation staff.

Use Case 11

11. **Nov 2024 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: High

Notes: Caveat here needs to be that DOI minting must be approved by a curator associated with that record, could be requested in the process of creating a SPASE record.

Users: [Mission data metadata contributors, Curation Staff, Mission data metadata contributors, Research data metadata contributors, Large research data metadata contributors]

Title: Create a PID for a dataset that has a SPASE record.

Description: User navigates to the dataset landing page and clicks on a button to request a PID (e.g. DOI). Any missing metadata required to create a PID is requested through the interface. The user supplies this information, completing the PID request. A notification is automatically generated and sent to curation staff and the metadata contributor for the dataset for approval. Once approved, the PID is automatically created, added to the SPASE record, propagated to all related metadata records for the dataset, and added to the landing page. If all the metadata required to create the PID exists in the SPASE metadata record, the PID is automatically created and propagated as described without any needed approvals. The user can now use the PID for the dataset.

Use Case 12

12. **Nov 2024 voting: 80%**

Priority: High

Notes: This is where the mission/instrument records come in, but no specific fields indicating. Descriptions and links to other items seem implied. The mission should be linked to the dataset through the instrument record. Showing both on the landing page can be done in that implementation, this doesn't necessarily require that missions be directly connected to the datasets in the metadata.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists, Students, Teacher and curriculum developers]

Title: Find more information about the instrument or mission the dataset is associated with.

Description: User is already on the landing page of a dataset they are interested in. User sees each of the names of the producing mission/observatory/etc and instrument

as a link and follows that link to a landing page for the instrument or mission/observatory/etc. The user uses this information to help determine the relevance of that dataset to their current workflow.

Use Case 13

13. **Nov 2024 voting: 73.33%**

Priority: High

Notes: Lean on VSO model and their implementation to incorporate wavelength in the proper way. Could lean on both ISTP and VSO for cadence. Wavelength could be a category, too (e.g. IR vs X-Ray).

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists, Teacher and curriculum developers, Students]

Title: Find solar data of a particular wavelength and cadence.

Description: The user is performing research comparing solar imagery of a particular range of spectral wavelengths. To simplify incorporating other datasets, the user desires datasets of a similar spectral wavelength and cadence in the same time span. The user navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface and searches for data of the desired spectral wavelength and cadence in the same time span as the other datasets they are already using. Several datasets are returned in the search results. The user is able to select datasets from these listed results based on the file formats, related software, and analysis instructions and examples included in the documentation and related publications.

Use Case 14

14. **Nov 2024 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: High

Notes: DataCite also has a list of [roles](#). Must allow terms from this and other vocabularies, maybe having a few 'blessed' ones integrated into the submission form but still allow others. For HDRL, would have to require contributors (not creators for now) to select a role from DataCite and then can add other roles as desired (e.g. PI, Co-I, etc).

Users: [Curation Staff, Mission data metadata contributors, Research data metadata contributors, Large research data metadata contributors]

Title: Add an author or person with another role to a SPASE dataset record and use a taxonomy of terms to indicate their role.

Description: The user edits the SPASE record by adding the first and last name of one or more people to the list of contributors to the record. The user has the option to include the ORCID, the associated institution, and the role from an external taxonomy (e.g. from the CRediT taxonomy <https://credit.niso.org/>) for each of the people added and for those

previously on the record.

Use Case 15

15. **Nov 2024 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: High

Notes: None

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, Students, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers]

Title: Assess and then share a link to a persistent dataset landing page.

Description: The user sees a post on Helionauts looking for a specific dataset. User uses the name of the dataset from the post in a text search either on the Heliophysics-wide search interface or through an internet search engine. The user discovers the link to the dataset landing page, navigates to that website, and determines the landing page has the information the user will likely need (e.g. links to download the data, links to references on how to use/analyze the data, etc). The user then responds to the post with a link to the landing page with a description of the data, links to download the data in various ways, links to how to analyze the data. (e.g. get ground magnetometer data from Goose Bay).

Use Case 16

16. **Nov 2024 voting: 73.33%**

Priority: High

Notes: Likely include the protocolName, access link, and doc link for each. Some protocol specific info may also be necessary, like the datasetID in that service, keywords, etc. This will likely get complex.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists]

Title: Access a specific type of data over a given time range that may be accessible through one or more access protocols.

Description: A user wants data of a given measurement type and time range available through their preferred protocol (e.g. HAPI, das2, etc). The user searches either via the Heliophysics-wide search interface, its API, or the internet to find the SPASE record which matches the desired time range and access protocol. The user is able to locate the desired dataset, confirm its availability through the desired protocol and the desired flavor (e.g., multiple https options), and incorporate it into their workflow.

Use Case 17

17. **Nov 2024 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: **Medium**

Notes: The metadata shown on the landing page should be prioritized in the requirements and supported in the structure, but the plotting capabilities are external to SPASE 3.0. Could be achieved in the implementation of the landing page instead.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists, Teacher and curriculum developers, Space weather forecasters, Heliophysics software services]

Title: Deciding whether to use a dataset.

Description: A user has selected a dataset in the search results of either an internet search or a search in a Heliophysics-wide search interface for further investigation. The user navigates to the landing page for the dataset to determine the relevance of the dataset to their work, potential analysis methods needed for the dataset, potential data storage needed, and further understanding of the dataset. The information presented in the search results is also presented on the landing page (e.g. dataset name, description, and so on). The user also discovers the parameters' names, units and descriptions on the landing page, the coordinate system for each parameter, the dimensionality of a parameter (e.g. restrict to vector quantities vs scalar), the estimated size of the dataset, and the name of the person to contact for more information/collaboration. The user determines that the parameters included in the dataset are relevant to their workflow, the coordinate system is acceptable (or requires conversion), the data storage required is not problematic (or requires cloud support), and decides to incorporate the dataset into their research. The user may also inspect a "slice" of the dataset (e.g. a scalar time series) rather than needing to "load" data elements that the user doesn't find relevant for selection decisions. The user is able to use the name of the contact person to find the contact information for that person via a web search or other method for further collaboration in their work using the dataset.

Use Case 18

18. **Nov 2024 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: **High**

Notes: Indicating links to other item types *does not* require that SPASE have records for those items. It does require that SPASE support external identifiers in a uniform way (e.g. URLs, identifiers from Software Heritage, DOIs, RORs, RRIIDs, etc).

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists, Space weather forecasters, Research data metadata contributors, Large research data metadata contributors]

Title: Interlinking items used in the creation of a new dataset in SPASE.

Description: A user has performed custom analysis on an existing dataset. While

creating the SPASE record, the user desires to link and indicate the relationship between the new dataset and the originating dataset, other datasets used to create the new product, the software used to perform the processing, and other artifacts used in the creation of the new dataset. The user is able to easily link those items and indicate the **specific provenance relationship** to the new dataset while creating the SPASE record for the new dataset. When the SPASE record is complete, these linked items are displayed on the landing page for the new dataset, and the new dataset is automatically linked to the other items on their landing pages and in their metadata records, with the changes automatically propagated to the related schema.org, DataCite, and any other repository-specific or general metadata records.

Use Case 19

19. **Nov 2024 voting: 73.33%**

Priority: **High**

Notes: FORCE11 guidelines for citing datasets require a version-specific citation, including a version-specific DOI. One example of how to organize DOIs is given by Zenodo, where a concept DOI is minted for the dataset as a whole and version-specific DOIs are minted for each version. The concept DOI serves as the connection piece to all version-specific DOIs. Landing pages of older versions should have a note at the top indicating there is a newer version available. Convention is that major versions require version-specific DOIs while minor versions do not. [Important pieces](#) include the version number, version date, version description, and temporal range(s), where temporal range is the time range where the changes between versions affected the data. The temporal range could be a single range or a list of ranges, preferably in the ISO time format.

Users: [Mission representatives]

Title: Mission team produces a new version of a mission dataset and needs to indicate this in the SPASE record for the dataset.

Description: The user updates the processing method for a given dataset of a given processing level and wishes for the public to use the new version of the dataset instead of the old one. The user wishes for the version change to be indicated in the SPASE record, displayed on the dataset landing page, and potentially indicated with a PID change. The user uploads the new version of the dataset to a domain-specific repository, quickly updates the SPASE record through an easy-to-use interface, performs any additional tasks required by the repository, and sees the dataset landing page updated in the Heliophysics-wide search interface. The dataset landing page has links to information about previous versions of the dataset. Other products generated with previous versions of the dataset remain linked on the dataset landing page.

Use Case 20

20. **Nov 2024 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: Medium

Notes: This is complex, should attempt to support in SPASE 3.0, but could postpone to SPASE 3.1 if necessary.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, Space weather forecasters, Research data metadata contributors, Large research data metadata contributors]

Title: Creating a SPASE record for a data catalog

Description: The user has participated in the production of several data catalogs. Some of the data catalogs are focused on a given phenomenon with multiple missions and instruments represented, while others are specific to a mission or instrument with several phenomena detected. The user is interested in having the catalog be included as a search result in the Heliophysics-wide search interface, so the user proceeds to submit the items and create SPASE records for each item through the submission interface. The user wants others to be able to find the catalog when searching for the missions or observatories associated with the catalog, the phenomenon(a), the measurement types, and the variables included in the catalog. So, for each catalog submission, the user indicates all datasets used to create the catalog, any software or other artifact used to analyze those datasets, the missions those data come from, the measurement types and parameter names in the catalog's column names, and phenomena included in the catalog, and indicates that the record is for a catalog (rather than a dataset). The user adds a good description to aid in users' understanding of the catalog, including an overview or example plot, and adds a link to the catalog's website. Once the SPASE record creation process is complete, the user is able to view the landing page for the submitted catalog on the Heliophysics-wide search interface and the catalog is included in the search results for search parameters aligning with the metadata. The tags for the landing page are automatically populated using metadata from the SPASE record.

Use Case 21

21. **Nov 2024 voting: 73.33%**

Priority: Medium

Notes: This is complex, should attempt to support in SPASE 3.0, but could postpone to SPASE 3.1 if necessary.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists, Space weather forecasters, Teacher and curriculum developers]

Title: Searching for an event catalog

Description: User is interested in finding a catalog of events for a given phenomenon or associated with a given mission or observatory. The user navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface, searches by the given phenomenon, mission or

observatory, in addition to any other relevant parameters (e.g. time range, measurement type, etc). The catalog is included in the search results and additionally separately indicated in the sidebar of the search interface as an item in the catalog category (as opposed to the dataset category). The user filters based on category type to only show catalogs in the search results and is able to find one or more catalogs suitable to their purpose. The user narrows down their selection based on the overview or example plots shown on the catalogs' landing pages, the parameter names and measurement types included in the catalogs' column headings, and other information conveyed in the descriptions. The user successfully finds a catalog relevant to their purpose.

Use Case 22

22. **Nov 2024 voting: 60%, adapted by group and approved Jan/Feb 2025.**

Priority: Medium

Notes: This is important to include to avoid potentially requiring updating the end date often. "Availability delay" is not to be taken as the recommended name of the metadata field. "Time range" would for example include an absolute stop date.

Users: [Space weather forecasters, Data Scientists, Heliophysics Researchers]

Title: Searching for datasets by availability delay

Description: The user is working to analyze a given event or potential event observed with real-time data from a mission a few days after the event. The user is interested in finding datasets for missions or observatories currently in operation with data available less than 3 days after the data was taken. The user searches by region and time range and is not successful since the metadata records are not updated in real-time. Instead, the user searches using other SPASE metadata which informs them on how up to date the datasets are likely to be and is able to find new datasets to aid in their analysis of the event of interest. The user then visits the dataset landing page to learn how to access the near-real time data (e.g. by data API or visiting the mission's science center website).

Use Case 23

23. **Mar 2025 voting: 83.33%**

Priority: High

Notes: None.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists]

Title: Discover solar and space physics (in-situ, space, and ground based) datasets using common metadata.

Description: User is performing a system science study of one or more common metadata such as observed regions, measurement types and time ranges. The user

navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface (website or API), searches by the time range, observed regions, and measurement types using the inputs on the search result interface. Datasets across many regions are presented to the user. The user then uses the information on the landing pages of a few datasets to narrow down the datasets they wish to attempt to use.

Use Case 24

24. **Mar 2025 voting: 100%**

Priority: High

Notes: Also mentioned in other use cases. Must be possible to use a term for phenomenon from an externally controlled vocabulary, including the associated subfield (e.g. inScheme, etc).

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists]

Title: Discover solar and space physics (in-situ, space, and ground based) datasets using phenomena.

Description: User is performing a system science study of one or more phenomena. The user navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface (website or API), types in the phenomenon name into the search bar, and is returned with many datasets related to that phenomenon. The user narrows down the search results by adding other relevant metadata using the inputs on the search result interface. The user then uses the information on the landing pages of a few datasets to narrow down the datasets they wish to attempt to use.

Use Case 25

25. **Mar 2025 voting: 100%**

Priority: High

Notes: Also discussed in other use cases.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Students, Data Scientists, Teacher and curriculum developers, Space weather forecasters]

Title: Find datasets related to a specific measurement type and subregion.

Description: The user visits a Heliophysics-wide data search interface to find datasets of a specific measurement type in other areas of Heliophysics. The user types in the measurement type into the text bar of the search interface and is presented with many search results. The user discovers that there are datasets of the same measurement type in other areas of Heliophysics. If there are many datasets, they narrow down the number of returned results by selecting the desired region and subregion, and investigate the remaining datasets for further investigation.

Use Case 26

26. **Mar 2025 voting: 83.33%**

Priority: High

Notes: In addition to measurement and mission in SPASE 3.0, need the search interface to have an 'exclude' type of search.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Students, Data Scientists, Space weather forecasters]

Title: Find datasets related to a specific measurement type but are not produced by a certain mission(s).

Description: The user visits a Heliophysics-wide data search interface to find datasets of a specific measurement type in other areas of Heliophysics. The user types in the measurement type into the text bar of the search interface and is presented with many search results. The user discovers that there are datasets of the same measurement type in other areas of Heliophysics. A list of missions the datasets are associated with becomes populated on the interface with the number of datasets matching the search request indicated near the mission name. The user ignores datasets linked to missions the user is already familiar with by deselecting the mission names on the interface. The user selects the datasets of interest from the remaining dataset options.

Use Case 27

27. **Mar 2025 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: Low

Notes: Related publication information should not be stored in SPASE, but can instead be extracted from external sources (e.g. Asclepius Broker) and presented to the user in the **interface**. The interoperability requirement of SPASE 3.0 results in these relation types being supported, but not prioritized. The region and measurement type are repeated from earlier use cases.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Students, Data Scientists, Space weather forecasters]

Title: Find datasets related to a specific measurement type, but is not cited in or otherwise linked to recent publications.

Description: The user visits a Heliophysics-wide data search interface to find datasets of a similar measurement type in other areas of Heliophysics. The user types in the measurement type into the text bar of the search interface and is presented with many search results. The user discovers that there are datasets of a similar measurement type in other areas of Heliophysics. If there are many datasets, they narrow down the number of returned results by selecting the desired region and subregion, and investigate the remaining datasets for further investigation. The interface also presents statistical information about the publication years of the publications linked to the datasets in the search result list. The user ignores datasets cited in or linked to publications published in

the past few years by restricting the publication year range accordingly.

Use Case 28

28. **Mar 2025 voting: 50%**

Priority: **Low**

Notes: Related publication information should not be stored in SPASE, but can instead be extracted from external sources (e.g. Asclepius Broker) and presented to the user in the **interface**. The interoperability requirement of SPASE 3.0 results in these relation types being supported, but not prioritized. The region and measurement type are repeated from earlier use cases.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Students, Data Scientists, Space weather forecasters]

Title: Find datasets related to a specific measurement type, but is not cited or otherwise linked to publications authored by close colleagues.

Description: The user visits a Heliophysics-wide data search interface to find datasets of a similar measurement type in other areas of Heliophysics. The user types in the measurement type into the text bar of the search interface and is presented with many search results. The user discovers that there are datasets of a similar measurement type in other areas of Heliophysics. If there are many datasets, they narrow down the number of returned results by selecting the desired region and subregion, and investigate the remaining datasets for further investigation. The interface also presents statistical information about the author names of the publications linked to the datasets in the search result list. The user ignores datasets cited in or linked to publications authored by close colleagues by excluding those authors from the list presented.

Use Case 29

29. **Mar 2025 voting: 50%**

Priority: **Medium**

Notes: This use case does not present a requirement on what fields to have particularly, other than PIDs (including URLs and DOIs), but rather prioritizes interoperability and serialization choices to enable the capabilities described.

Users: [Data Scientists]

Title: Use SPASE records to build an RDF knowledge graph.

Description: User wants to compare or connect heliophysics resources using knowledge graphs in order to promote discoverability of these combined resources. They obtain SPASE dataset metadata records and use them to produce an RDF knowledge graph in a standard way. Specifically, the user assembles an RDF knowledge graph of Heliophysics resources that pulls from Heliophysics dataset represented in SPASE, such that entities with identifiers (e.g., other datasets, publications, software, funding, people,

instruments, missions, observatories, and institutions) referenced in the SPASE record are represented in consistent ways or other domains that would provide contextualization (e.g., areas of Earth and planetary science, Astrophysics). The user is able to easily combine the RDF generated from SPASE records with RDF generated from resources in other fields to perform the comparison and enhance discovery.

Use Case 30

30. **Mar 2025 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: High

Notes: Due to policy requirements at NASA, we need both data and metadata licenses represented properly (e.g. similar to DataCite method) in the SPASE 3.0 structure.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists, Teacher and curriculum developers, Students]

Title: Search for a dataset by their associated usage licenses allowed by their institution.

Description: User uses a common internet search engine or the heliophysics-wide search interface (website or API) to discover heliophysics datasets and other linked resources. The user is restricted by their host entity (e.g. home institution) to only use data with the CC0 or CC-BY licenses. The user enters any desired restrictions on the search interface and is presented with a list of datasets. Also presented on the interface is statistical information on the usage licenses associated with the datasets (not the metadata). The user further restricts their search to only include datasets with those licenses by selecting those license options. The user selects one of the listed datasets and navigates to the landing page for more information. The user compares this information across multiple datasets to determine which datasets to investigate further for inclusion into their work.

Use Case 31

31. **Mar 2025 voting: 83.33%**

Priority: High

Notes: Preference is to delegate person information to ORCID and external services instead of having person records in SPASE. Instead, prefer to imitate DataCite's approach where the information per person/creator/contributor is entered into each dataset record. This greatly simplifies the creation of dataset records in SPASE since there will be no need to create separate person records beforehand.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists, Teacher and curriculum developers]

Title: Finding a person to help them in using a given dataset (included in the SPASE record).

Description: The user uses either an internet search engine, the Heliophysics-wide

search interface, or the PID to navigate to the dataset's landing page. The user looks through the dataset contacts listed in the SPASE record to determine potential contacts for questions about the dataset. If the listed contact has an ORCID listed in the SPASE record, the user uses the information from ORCID to contact the person. If the person has no ORCID and an email is listed, the user contacts the person via the listed email.

Use Case 32

32. **Mar 2025 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: High

Notes: This use case is referring to “reference publications” and documentation for the dataset and the related instrument. These publications *should* be represented in the SPASE record for the dataset. If the related publication is for the related instrument, it should also be included in the instrument record. Other related publication information should not be stored in SPASE, but can instead be extracted from external sources (e.g. Asclepius Broker) and presented to the user in the **interface**, which could also be used in the way described in this use case. A current problem is that the links between dataset and instruments and instruments and observatories are one-way but should be two-way, as in each observatory should have a list of the instruments it hosted/hosts in addition to the instrument being linked to the observatory and similar for datasets. Should **discuss** whether the observatory should be directly linked to the dataset or only linked through the generating instrument.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, Data Scientists, Teacher and curriculum developers]

Title: Finding a person to help them in using a given dataset (linked from the SPASE record).

Description: The user uses either an internet search engine, the Heliophysics-wide search interface, or the PID to navigate to the dataset's landing page. The user has previously attempted without success to contact the people listed in the SPASE record indicated as the proper data contacts. The user now looks for publications linked to the dataset since most publications list the email address of the first author. The user collects a few contact names and email addresses from the linked publications and proceeds to contact those people for help with the dataset.

Use Case 33

33. **Mar 2025 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: Low

Notes: Fields that seem to be required for this are description and keywords. Otherwise, this reads like a service to be provided rather than something internal to SPASE.

Users: [Data Scientists, Curation Staff, Agency representatives, Heliophysics software

services]

Title: Determine how often terms are used in dataset descriptions associated with a specific mission.

Description: The user is asked to analyze the descriptions of dataset metadata records associated with a given mission to determine the frequency of terms used. If highly used terms are not associated with keywords for the specific mission, then they will be added as keywords. The user uses the search interface to search for datasets associated with the given mission. The search interface also presents statistical information for the description fields of the datasets included in the search results. The user uses this statistical presentation to determine what terms are above a specific usage threshold and records this list. The user then compares this list with terms already associated with the mission (e.g. measurement types, phenomena, and so on) and removes those terms from their list. The user then presents the list of the remaining terms and their associated usage frequencies to the appropriate people for potential addition to the mission either as general keywords or as part of existing vocabularies (whether in SPASE or managed externally).

Use Case 34

34. **Mar 2025 voting: 50%**

Priority: High

Notes: *Provenance relationships* should be included in the SPASE records, including dataset generation by specific software versions, previous versions and similar information. However, relationships to items external to SPASE can be stored elsewhere and retrieved through citation tracking services (e.g. related software and related publications beyond documentation and reference publications). Also noting that the actions this use case described are likely to be taken to assess research impact of a given dataset/mission, which could be used to determine funding decisions.

Users: [Data Scientists, Curation Staff, Agency representatives, Heliophysics software services]

Title: Determine how many people, publications and softwares are connected to datasets associated with a specific mission.

Description: The user has been instructed to gather the number of entities, artifacts, and people associated with data produced by a specific mission as supporting evidence of data impact to argue for additional mission funding. The user uses the search interface's API to search for all datasets produced by the specified mission. In that call, the user includes dataset names, dataset authors, related publications, related software, and related datasets as the fields to be returned. The user then iterates through the returned information using the search interface's API to retrieve the associated authors for each related dataset. The API returns a predefined error value for requested datasets not represented in the database, which the user accounts for in the script. The user completes the author list by adding authors of the related publications, related software, and the remaining related datasets through external means (e.g. the authors listed in the

metadata of those items' DOIs obtained through a separate API). The user then presents these statistics to the proposal leads for potential inclusion in the proposal.

Use Case 35

35. **Mar 2025 voting: 83.33%**

Priority: High

Notes: Comments coming in a separate document.

Users: [Data Scientists, Curation Staff, Agency representatives, Heliophysics software services]

Title: Determine the presence of a long list of fields in support of FAIR for datasets hosted by a specific data repository.

Description: The user is asked to analyze the SPASE metadata records for data hosted by a specific data repository for FAIR. The user has a long list of properties to obtain statistics for, which necessitates the use of the search interface's API for efficiency. The user makes a call to the API for all datasets hosted by the specific data repository and includes in the call the desired return fields for each dataset. For a reasonable FAIR analysis, the user decides to analyze the metadata based on the information in the following fields: dataset name, dataset description, dataset usage license, metadata usage license, dataset PID, dataset access methods, related software, related publications, links to dataset documentation, author ORCiDs, keywords, associated instruments, observed regions, related phenomena, temporal range of the data, measurement types, parameters, parameter units, and the ROR of the hosting repository. The subfields of related artifacts are checked for PIDs. Text-based fields are checked for the use of terms from controlled vocabularies, including the presence of URIs associated with both the controlled vocabularies used and the individual terms. The user completes their analysis of the records based on these metadata and presents that information to their superiors.

Use Case 36

36. **Mar 2025 voting: 83.33%**

Priority: High

Notes: Need to indicate access protocol types in the dataset records. Would be beneficial for search for access methods/protocols to be terms in a controlled vocabulary. Likely SPASE controlled, but depends on contributions from the community (especially those in charge of those access methods).

Users: [Heliophysics Researcher, Data Scientist, Heliophysics software services]

Title: Search for datasets by available access methods or protocols.

Description: The user already has an established workflow using a particular type of access point or protocol, and so wishes to limit dataset additions to those available

through the chosen access point or protocol. The user enters the desired search terms into the Heliophysics-wide search interface and additionally restricts the search by selecting the desired type of access point or protocol in the search interface. The user selects the desired datasets from the returned list.

Use Case 37

37. **Mar 2025 voting: 100%**

Priority: High

Notes: Need sufficient information for the dataset for each access protocol to formulate the call to that access method (e.g. key value for the dataset/parameter/etc). Intending to use this to provide the “click button” feature described below for the landing page.

Users: [Heliophysics Researcher, Data Scientist, Heliophysics software services]

Title: Retrieve data from a dataset with a selected access method using the dataset landing page.

Description: The user has selected one dataset to add to their workflow from the Heliophysics-wide search interface that all have the same type of access method or protocol. The user now wants to manually download or otherwise interact with a portion of that dataset through the selected access method or protocol. The user navigates to the landing page of that dataset and is able to click on the desired access method or protocol to arrive at a specially designed interface for that data. The user then proceeds to retrieve or otherwise interact with that data through an external interface, access method or protocol using the instructions available through that service.

Use Case 38

38. **Mar 2025 voting: 83.33%**

Priority: High

Notes: Need sufficient information for the dataset for each access protocol to formulate the call to that access method (e.g. key value for the dataset/parameter/etc). Intending to use this to provide the feature described below for the landing page.

Users: [Heliophysics Researcher, Data Scientist, Heliophysics software services]

Title: Build a workflow for automated access to data using the search interface’s API and information about the data access method or protocol.

Description: The user has selected several datasets to add to their workflow from the Heliophysics-wide search interface that all have the same type of access method or protocol. The user now wants to add those datasets via a script or notebook in an automatic method. The user uses the search interface’s API to retrieve the information associated with the selected access method or protocol and, in combination with the user’s previously existing understanding of that access method or protocol’s syntax, is able to construct a working script to retrieve the desired data from the access method or

protocol. (Users not having this pre-existing understanding of the access method or protocol would need a link to documentation for the access method or protocol to perform the same task.)

Use Case 39

39. **Mar 2025 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: **High** (for the base functionality, e.g. searching by start/stop time, instrument, observatory, measurement type) and **Medium** (to handle the multiple and potentially discontinuous time ranges per dataset hosted by the repository).

Notes: Time ranges held in different repositories can be discontinuous and spread out in unexpected ways. We will need the ground-based community to help us get this type of search correct.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers]

Title: Searching for a data split across many repositories associated with an instrument and ground station (observatory) each with multiple identifiers.

Description: User is attempting to search for a specific time range of a ground-based dataset generated by specific instrument at an observatory that is stored across many repositories (e.x. Ottawa 1989 magnetometer data). The user tries a few known repositories and cannot find the section of the data desired. The user then navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface and searches for the data by the specific time range, the instrument and observatory name or one of the multiple identifiers of each of these, and the measurement type (e.g. ground magnetometers / magnetic field) and is able to locate all datasets which satisfy those parameters. Data from different instruments and observatories are represented as different datasets in the search results. The user navigates to each of the SPASE landing pages and from each selects one or more datasets which have the data of interest and download each of them. They use the SPASE descriptions to help merge these data into a dataset which they may use for their science.

Use Case 40

40. **Mar 2025 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: **Medium**

Notes: Not related to items internal to SPASE, but to a service. Should consider structures in the systems we need to map to (e.g. DataCite, Schema.org, HAPI, etc) as potential solutions to simplify mappings to those systems.

Users: [Automated curation services]

Title: Updating metadata in SPASE from metadata hosted in an access method or protocol.

Description: Metadata for a given dataset exists both in a data access method or protocol and in its SPASE record. Maintainers of the external metadata for the dataset discover an outdated or incorrect metadata field and update that information in the

protocol's metadata record. An automated metadata check is scheduled to run at regular intervals (e.g. weekly) to compare SPASE records with metadata records maintained by access methods or protocols. To keep the metadata in the related SPASE records up to date, the user checks for all changes in that metadata since the last time it was executed. The user notes all changes that are relevant to SPASE records, finds the related SPASE records and begins the process for updating that information, subject to review by a SPASE curator.

Use Case 41

41. **Mar 2025 voting: 50%**

Priority: Medium

Notes: Not related to items internal to SPASE, but to a service. Should consider structures in the systems we need to map to (e.g. DataCite, Schema.org, HAPI, etc) as potential solutions to simplify mappings to those systems.

Users: [Automated curation services]

Title: Updating metadata in an access method or protocol record based on metadata updates in SPASE.

Description: Metadata for a given dataset exists both in a data access method or protocol and in its SPASE record. Maintainers of the SPASE metadata for the dataset discover an outdated or incorrect metadata field and update that information in the SPASE metadata record. An automated metadata check is scheduled to run at regular intervals (e.g. weekly) to compare SPASE records with metadata records maintained by access methods or protocols. To keep the metadata in the access method or protocol's record up to date, the user checks for all changes in the related SPASE metadata records since the last time it was executed via an API, specifically searching for all SPASE records modified since a certain date and having the specified access method or protocol. The user notes all changes that are relevant to the access method or protocol's records, finds those records, and begins the process for updating that information, subject to review by a curator on their team.

Use Case 42

42. **Mar 2025 voting: 66.67%**

Priority: Medium

Notes: Not related to items internal to SPASE, but to a service. Should consider structures in the systems we need to map to (e.g. DataCite, Schema.org, HAPI, etc) as potential solutions to simplify mappings to those systems.

Users: [Automated curation services]

Title: Updating metadata in SPASE from metadata hosted by a data repository.

Description: Metadata for a given dataset exists both in a data repository, whether

domain-specific or generic, and in its SPASE record. Maintainers of the data repository's metadata or dataset authors for the dataset discover an outdated or incorrect metadata field in their records and update that information in their metadata record. An automated metadata check is scheduled to run at regular intervals (e.g. weekly) to compare SPASE records with metadata records maintained by that data repository. To keep the metadata in the related SPASE records up to date, the user checks for all changes in the data repository's metadata since the last time it was executed. The user notes all changes that are relevant to SPASE records, finds the related SPASE records and begins the process for updating that information, subject to review by a SPASE curator.

Use Case 43

43. **Mar 2025 voting: 50%**

Priority: Medium

Notes: Not related to items internal to SPASE, but to a service. Should consider structures in the systems we need to map to (e.g. DataCite, Schema.org, HAPI, etc) as potential solutions to simplify mappings to those systems.

Users: [Automated curation services]

Title: Updating metadata in a data repository record based on metadata updates in SPASE.

Description: Metadata for a given dataset exists both in a data repository and in its SPASE record. Maintainers of the SPASE metadata for the dataset discover an outdated or incorrect metadata field in their records and update that information in the SPASE metadata record. An automated metadata check is scheduled to run at regular intervals (e.g. weekly) to compare SPASE records with metadata records maintained by the associated data repository. To keep the metadata in the related data repository records up to date, the user checks for all changes in the SPASE metadata since the last time it was executed via an API, specifically searching for all SPASE records modified since a certain date and having the associated data repository. The user notes all changes that are relevant to SPASE records, finds the related SPASE records and begins the process for updating that information, subject to review by a data repository curator.

Use Case 44

44. **Mar 2025 voting: 50%**

Priority: Medium

Notes: Not related to items internal to SPASE, but to a service. Should consider structures in the systems we need to map to (e.g. DataCite, Schema.org, HAPI, etc) as potential solutions to simplify mappings to those systems.

Users: [Curation Staff, Mission data metadata contributors, Research data metadata contributor, Large research data metadata contributors, Automated curation services]

Title: Creating a draft SPASE record from metadata hosted in an external access method or protocol.

Description: Metadata for many Heliophysics datasets not described in a SPASE record are served through a given access method or service call with associated metadata. The user desires to add those datasets to the Heliophysics-wide data search interface by creating SPASE records for them. The user triggers a service to create draft SPASE records from the access method or protocol's metadata records based on a known mapping between SPASE metadata and the metadata structure of the access method or protocol. The user checks the draft records, performs any changes needed, and publishes the SPASE records.

Use Case 45

45. **Mar 2025 voting: 50%**

Priority: **Medium**

Notes: Previous discussion is to support research data in SPASE, but not restrict the required fields in SPASE 3.0 based on this support. The service mentioned in the description below is separate from the SPASE 3.0 model. See use case 4 for more details.

Users: [Curation Staff, ~~Mission data metadata contributors~~, Research data metadata contributor, Large research data metadata contributors, Automated curation services]

Title: Creating a draft SPASE record from metadata hosted in an external data generic repository.

Description: Metadata for many Heliophysics datasets not described in a SPASE record are served through an external generic repository (e.g. Zenodo) with associated metadata. The user desires to add those datasets to the Heliophysics-wide data search interface by creating SPASE records for them. The user triggers a service to create draft SPASE records from the generic repository's metadata records based on a known mapping between SPASE metadata and the metadata structure of the generic repository. The user checks the draft records, performs any changes needed, and publishes the SPASE records. (Domain-specific repositories will need to create a mapping to/from SPASE before SPASE records can be drafted. Generic repositories such as Zenodo are already compatible with DataCite DOIs and so can be easily incorporated through a single mapping.)

Use Case 46

46. **Mar 2025 voting: 50%**

Priority: **Low**

Notes: Implementation/service idea, not to determine what fields go into SPASE 3.0.

Users: [Curation Staff, Mission data metadata contributors, Research data metadata

contributor, Large research data metadata contributors, Automated curation services]

Title: Creating a draft SPASE record from information in an online OSDMP tool or similar online service.

Description: Metadata for future Heliophysics datasets exist in an online OSDMP tool or similar online service. The user desires to add those datasets to the Heliophysics-wide data search interface by creating SPASE records for them. The user triggers a service to create draft SPASE records from an API offered by the online OSDMP tool based on a known mapping between SPASE metadata and the metadata structure of that tool. The user checks the draft records and works towards completing the SPASE record as the research effort progresses.

Use Case 47

47. **Mar 2025 voting: 50%**

Priority: **Low**

Notes: See notes of use case 32 about what is needed for instrument and observatory records. The integration with an online OSDMP tool is an implementation/service idea, not to determine what fields go into SPASE 3.0.

Users: [Curation Staff, Mission data metadata contributors, Research data metadata contributor, Large research data metadata contributors, Automated curation services]

Title: Creating a draft SPASE record for a mission, observatory or other group of instruments from information in an online OSDMP tool or similar online service.

Description: Metadata for a future Heliophysics mission, observatory, or other group of instruments exist in an online OSDMP tool or similar online service. The user desires to add that item to the Heliophysics-wide data search interface by creating a SPASE record for them. The user triggers a service to create draft SPASE records from an API offered by the online OSDMP tool based on a known mapping between SPASE metadata for the item and the metadata structure of that tool. The user checks the draft records and works towards completing the SPASE record for the mission, observatory, or other group of instruments as the research effort progresses.

Use Case 48

48. **Mar 2025 voting: 50%**

Priority: **Low**

Notes: See notes of use case 32 about what is needed for instrument and observatory records. The integration with an online OSDMP tool is an implementation/service idea, not to determine what fields go into SPASE 3.0.

Users: [Curation Staff, Mission data metadata contributors, Research data metadata contributor, Large research data metadata contributors, Automated curation services]

Title: Creating a draft SPASE record for an instrument from information in an online

OSDMP tool or similar online service.

Description: Metadata for future Heliophysics instruments exist in an online OSDMP tool or similar online service. The user desires to add those instruments to the Heliophysics-wide data search interface by creating a SPASE record for them. The user triggers a service to create draft SPASE records for those instruments from an API offered by the online OSDMP tool based on a known mapping between SPASE metadata for instruments and the metadata structure of that tool. The user checks the draft records and works towards completing the SPASE record for the instruments as the research effort progresses.

Use Case 49

49. **Mar 2025 voting: 83.33%**

Priority: High

Notes: If DOIs are chosen, then those minimal fields are needed, plus a description and license, likely also ORCiDs, affiliations, affiliation RORs, funding information with identifiers (funding ROR, award title, award number), NASA-specific keywords (e.g. Heliophysics). Based on feedback from mission representatives, also need a place for a “Cite with” or “Cite As” to indicate reference publications. See use case 32 notes for additional fields (e.g. member instruments). [RRiDs](#) may also be chosen, but DOIs more likely.

Users: [Mission data metadata contributors, Curation Staff]

Title: Create a Persistent Identifier (PID) for a mission, observatory, group of instruments, or individual instruments described in a SPASE record.

Description: The user navigates to the SPASE landing page for the mission, observatory, group of instruments, or individual instrument and needs to request a persistent identifier for the item (e.g. a DOI). The user authenticates and navigates to the correct request page. The user is then presented with an interface indicating the metadata needed to complete the request. The user fills in the required metadata fields and potentially some additional fields and submits the request. A SPASE curator reviews and approves the request after any needed changes are made. All dataset records associated with that item are then automatically populated with the new PID for that mission, observatory, group of instruments, or instrument. The new PID is also automatically added to all SPASE records for related missions, observatories, groups of instruments, or other instruments.

Use Case 50

50. **Mar 2025 voting: 100%**

Priority: High

Notes: Differentiating between region (e.g. observation area) vs observatory location

(e.g. lat/lon coordinates on the ground vs type(?) of space orbit). In some cases, these will be equivalent (e.g. MMS), but that is not always the case.

User: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers]

Title: Find data according to the location of the observatory, mission, or other named group of instruments.

Description: The user navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface and enters the desired search terms, resulting in a list of matching datasets. The user desires to additionally filter based on the location of the observatory, particularly on whether the data was taken from space or from the ground, but is not familiar with what observatory and mission are of each type for every dataset listed. The user clicks on a portion of the search interface and is presented with the number of datasets associated with an observatory on the ground and the number of datasets associated with a space-based mission. The user clicks the desired observation/mission location on the interface and is presented with a list containing only datasets matching the chosen location type and the previously entered search terms. The user investigates the remaining datasets further.

Use Case 51

51. **Aug 2025 voting: 75%**

Priority: **High**

Note: version numbers, version dates, version descriptions.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers]

Title: A user working to replicate a data analysis needs to understand the differences between data versions.

Description: User is working to replicate an analysis described in a previously published research publication that used a dataset described by a SPASE record, but has discovered potential errors in the published result. The citation in the publication leads them to a landing page for the dataset which contains enough information for the user to confirm that the dataset is the same as the one used in the publication (e.g. dataset name, full citation, description, and so on), but is several versions later than the one used in the publication. The user is able to find the data version history of the dataset indicated on the landing page and is able to use the data version numbers, data version dates, and data version notes of each subsequent version to approximate what changes should be expected in the user's analysis compared to the published research.

Use Case 52

52. **Aug 2025 voting: 62.5%**

Priority: **Medium**

Note: Medium until we have a pipeline where such information can be automatically generated and added into the SPASE record without curator involvement. Important for

reproducibility, BUT too hard to do without software. Could alternatively provide this in the version description instead.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers]

Title: A user working to replicate a data analysis needs to understand the temporal ranges affected by different data versions.

Description: User is working to replicate an analysis described in a previously published research publication that used a dataset described by a SPASE record, but has discovered potential errors in the published result. The citation in the publication leads them to a landing page for the dataset which contains enough information for the user to confirm that the dataset is the same as the one used in the publication (e.g. dataset name, full citation, description, and so on), but is several versions later than the one used in the publication. The user is able to find the data version history of the dataset indicated on the landing page and is able to use the data version history and the affected temporal ranges of each subsequent version to determine whether the given data analysis should produce significantly different results in the user's analysis using the current version of the data compared to the published research that used an older version. *(This use case is similar to the previous one, but separates out the affected temporal ranges from the other version fields.)*

Use Case 53

53. **Aug 2025 voting: 100%**

Priority: High

Note: acknowledgement field

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, Mission representatives, Mission data metadata contributors, Research data metadata contributors, Large research data metadata contributors]

Title: User is required by their funding source to include a specific acknowledgement statement on the dataset landing page.

Description: The user is required by their funding source to include a specific acknowledgement statement on the dataset landing page. The user navigates to the relevant metadata submission interface, is able to easily find the correct field to enter this information, and copies the required statement into that field in SPASE. The required acknowledgement statement is then prominently shown on the generated dataset landing page as required by the funding source.

Use Case 54

54. **Aug 2025 voting: 75%**

Priority: High

Note: Need some simple list of terms for users to choose from. Existing list: Raw, uncalibrated, calibrated, value-added. This list can be revised. Individual repositories will

need to map their repository-specific processing levels to these when the list is completed / reviewed by the community.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, (meta) Data Scientists]

Title: User wants to search for data based on a generic processing level across multiple repositories.

Description: A user wants to search for data based on a generic processing level (e.g. raw data vs science-ready) across multiple repositories. The user navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface and indicates a few search options in that interface. A large number of datasets are presented of varying data processing levels, which the user then narrows down their search by selecting an option for science-ready data. All lower data processing levels are then removed from the search results, allowing the user to continue narrowing down their search by other factors.

Use Case 55

55. **Aug 2025 voting: 100%**

Priority: **High**

Note: adding measurement type to the instruments/etc.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, (meta) Data Scientists, Space weather forecasters]

Title: User wants to search for an instrument, instrument suite, or mission/observatory by the associated measurement type(s).

Description: A user wants to search for an instrument/instrument suite, or mission/observatory by the associated measurement type(s). The user enters a few common terms into the search interface and is presented with data, instruments, and missions matching those terms. The user narrows down the search by indicating one or more measurement types and is presented with data, instruments, and missions associated with those measurement types. The user further selects based on the specific type of object desired (e.g. instrument vs mission) and is able to compare between those object types associated with the selected measurement type(s).

Use Case 56

56. **Aug 2025 voting: 75%**

Priority: **Medium**

Note: Would need to implement this *with* the below use case. We would put the specific position in the observatory / instrument record, not the dataset record.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, (meta) Data Scientists]

Title: User wants to search for a ground observatory or instrument by its specific position on a planetary body (e.g. Earth).

Description: The user navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface and enters the desired search terms, including time range, measurement type and observatory or

instrument region, and indicates that the search is for observatories or instruments (e.g. magnetometers) rather than datasets. The resulting page with the list of matching observatories and instruments also includes additional options. The user selects the desired object type and the latitude range and is presented with the final list, which the user further investigates by navigating to the indicated landing pages.

Use Case 57

57. **Aug 2025 voting: 87.5%**

Priority: Medium

Note: Would need to implement this *with* the above use case.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, (meta) Data Scientists]

Title: User wants to find datasets associated with ground instruments or observatories by its specific position on the indicated planetary body.

Description: The user navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface and enters the desired search terms, including time range, measurement type and observatory region. The resulting page with the list of matching datasets also includes additional options. The user selects the observatory latitude and longitude ranges and is presented with the final dataset list, which the user further investigates by navigating to the dataset landing pages.

Use Case 58

58. **Aug 2025 voting: 75%**

Priority: Medium

Note: Definitely needs this in documentation outside of SPASE, but searching by coordinate system and specific measurement ranges might be better in software. Searching by region is already a high priority based on other use cases.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, (meta) Data Scientists]

Title: User wants to find datasets associated with measurements in a given region within specific measurement ranges in a given coordinate system.

Description: The user navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface and enters the desired search terms, including time range, measurement type and observed region, where the measurement type and observed region terms may be sourced from a controlled vocabulary external to SPASE. The resulting page with the list of matching datasets also includes an option to select data spatial coverage. The user selects the latitude, longitude and altitude ranges and is presented with the final dataset list, which the user further investigates by navigating to the dataset landing pages.

Use Case 59

59. **Aug 2025 voting: 87.5%**

Priority: High

Note: parameter type for datasets (e.g., Electric field, magnetic field, particles, etc)

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers, (meta) Data Scientists]

Title: User wants to find datasets associated with a parameter type in a given region.

Description: The user navigates to the Heliophysics-wide search interface and enters the desired search terms, including time range, measurement type and observed region. The resulting page with the list of matching datasets also includes an option to select parameter type. The user selects the parameter type (e.g. alpha particle density), potentially sourced from a controlled vocabulary external to SPASE, and is presented with the final dataset list, which the user further investigates by navigating to the dataset landing pages.

Use Case 60

60. **Aug 2025 voting: 100%**

Priority: High

Note: Tricky to implement, but high need. Should look into this, particularly for solar data where mirroring is common practice. Could have a SPASE record for the group of datasets but no license, then have sub-datasets for the items at each repository with the correct license indicated for that repository. These 'sub-datasets' would be related to the high level one with an 'IsPartOf' relationship. This would avoid creating new structures, but may complicate search.

Note: What restrictions, if any, should be enforced as a prerequisite for a repository to create SPASE records? Should any requirement of permanence of a sunset plan be needed?

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers]

Title: For a dataset served from multiple data repositories, a user needs to explicitly identify the dataset license at each data repository to comply with their legal restrictions.

Description: Using the Heliophysics-wide search interface, the user identified a dataset potentially useful in the user's research project. The user navigates to the dataset landing page to find ways to access data and is presented with a list of repositories from which the dataset can be accessed. For each data repository serving the dataset, the dataset license is explicitly included. The user uses this information to access the dataset from a repository with a suitable license.

Use Case 61

61. **Aug 2025 voting: 87.5%**

Priority: High

Note: Similar to DataCite

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers]

Title: User needs to use metadata associated with the indicated related resources on the dataset landing page to identify which resources must be studied further.

Description: Using the Heliophysics-wide search interface, the user identified a dataset potentially useful in the user's research project. The user navigates to the dataset landing page and studies the information about the dataset. A list of related resources is also displayed on the dataset landing page, including resource type (e.g. software vs dataset), relation type (e.g. cites vs provenance relationships), resource URL, and resource name. The user uses this information to understand which related resources must be studied further to completely understand and correctly use the dataset.

Use Case 62

62. **Aug 2025 voting: 75%**

Priority: Medium

Note: description field in the related resource containers

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers]

Title: User wants to use the descriptions of the indicated related resources on the dataset landing page to identify which resources must be studied further.

Description: Using the Heliophysics-wide search interface, the user identified a dataset potentially useful in the user's research project. The user navigates to the dataset landing page and studies the information about the dataset. A list of related resources with some minimal metadata is also displayed on the dataset landing page, including resource type, relation type, resource URL, and resource name. The user determines this information is not enough to determine which resources should be prioritized, so the user additionally considers the resource descriptions to understand which related resources must be studied further to completely understand and correctly use the dataset.

Use Case 63

63. **Aug 2025 voting: 50%**

Priority: Low

Note: How to make sure solar is supported? Think about this. The trick may be in the definition of the field. Just use the ISO standard for time durations, but will need to translate on the landing pages.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers]

Title: User uses information on the dataset landing page to identify the differences between the measurement cadence and measurement interval (exposure).

Description: Using the Heliophysics-wide search interface, the user identifies a dataset potentially useful in the user's research project. The user navigates to the dataset landing page and studies information about the dataset. In addition to measurement cadence (interval between successive measurements), the dataset landing page also includes measurement interval (e.g., duration or exposure length of a measurement). The user identifies that the measurement interval is much shorter than the measurement cadence and uses this information to determine relevance of the data to the user's science question.

Use Case 64

64. **Aug 2025 voting: 50%**

Priority: **Low**

Note: Let's see how SPASE 3.0 works for everyone and then see if this is still needed.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, Mission representatives, Mission data metadata contributors]

Title: User wants to include on the dataset landing page additional metadata that cannot be described using SPASE data model standard fields.

Description: User submitting dataset SPASE description decides that additional metadata, that cannot be described using SPASE data model standard fields, may be useful to include on the dataset landing page. The user navigates to the metadata submission interface and finds that additional metadata can be included via a metadata extension field, which supports including both property name with globally unique PID and value with globally unique PID. The user is also offered the option of including a PID (e.g. a URL) for another metadata record. After submitting the dataset description, the additional metadata is then displayed on the dataset landing page through a metadata import system aligned with the given structure.

Use Case 65

65. **Aug 2025 voting: 100%**

Priority: **High**

Note: will use Bob Weigel's work and IVOA infrastructure for the coordinate taxonomy.

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers]

Title: User needs to understand coordinates and units metadata for the parameter components to make a final decision on relevance to their science question.

Description: Using the Heliophysics-wide search interface, the user identified a dataset potentially useful in the user's research project. The user navigates to the dataset landing page and studies information about the dataset. The user can see that parameter component metadata also includes parameter dimension sizes, the associated coordinate system, and the units of those coordinates. As an example, the user can see the parameter's associated coordinate system component names, and their units with any associated PIDs for those terms (e.g., if from a controlled vocabulary, internal or external to SPASE). These metadata provide the user with the final details needed to determine the relevance of the data to the user's science question.

Use Case 66

66. **Aug 2025 voting: 87.5%**

Priority: High

Note: Need max and min with units for each, and a name for the range (ideally from a controlled list of some sort).

Users: [Heliophysics Researchers, non-Heliophysics and new to Heliophysics Researchers]

Title: User is searching for parameter measurements in a given wavelength or energy range that has multiple range definitions.

Description: Using the Heliophysics-wide search interface, the user searches for parameter measurements in a given wavelength or energy range by the common name of that range (e.g., infrared or UV), where the common names may be sourced from a community-managed controlled vocabulary (internal or external to SPASE). However, the interface returns datasets with parameters that are irrelevant to the user's science question due to the varying maximum and minimum limits commonly associated with that named range. The user then enters a maximum and/or minimum wavelength or energy with the associated units to narrow down their search for relevant data. The user is then able to select several datasets for further exploration. (*Wavelength and energy range are just two examples. This use case also applies to other parameter range types, such as angles, mass, and frequency.*)